

Country code				IT		Project		Mulch		Extraction method			Berlese-Tullgren		Extraction days		15																				
Land use				2.1_Arable_land		Dominant plant species		NA			pH(H2O)		7.34																								
Farming system				NA		Tillage system		Strip_tillage			Last tillage event (yyyy-mm-dd)		2023-10-15																								
Cropping system				Monoculture		Fertilizer type		NPK_fertilizer			Last fertilizer application		2024-06-09																								
Soil type (WRB-RSG)				Cambisols		Soil textural class		NA			Type main crop		Perennial			Irrigation type		Drip_irrigation			Last irrigation event (yyyy-mm-dd)		2024-09-27														
Site/Field		RC		Treatment		T4		Block		not		Abundance (n) or Presence (-99)			Tillage depth (cm)		20			Main Plant Protection Products (PPP)			Insecticide			Last PPP application		2024-07-31									
Subph. ^a / class ^b		Biological Form (BF)		Eco-morphological Index (EMI)		Description		Replicate ID 1		Replicate ID 2		Replicate ID 3		Refer. Note		QBS-ar EMI		EMI all BFs		Mean density (n m ⁻²)		Relative abund.(%)		Ab. Class (n m ⁻²)		EMI Replicates			Spectral communities comparison								
								4A		4B		4C														R1		R2		R3		R1-R2		R1-R3		R2-R3	
Chelicerata / Arachnida	Acari	20	mites: single unit, compact, unsegmented body	also Oribatida	108	233	221		20	20	18733	68	B	20	20	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	Araneae	01	spiders (fangs chelicerae, cephalothorax + abdomen) length ≥ 5mm						5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
		05	spiders < 5mm & scarcely pigmented				1			5	33	0	E	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0			
	Pseudoscorpiones	20	false scorpions: like tiny scorpions without telson				1	1		20	20	67	0	E	0	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20			
	Opliones	10	harvestmen: eyes, 2 body segments fusion, generally long legs							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Palpigradi	20	microship scorpions: locomotion palps and whip-like flagellum						0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Crust.	Isopoda	10	woodlice: 7 pairs of jointed limbs, 2 pairs of antennae (1 pair longer)			1	1		10	10	67	0	E	0	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10			
	Diplopoda	10	millipedes: cylindrical body, 2 pairs of legs per seg. after the 4 th		2				20	10	67	0	E	10	0	0	10	0	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10			
		20	millipedes < 5mm or Polyxenida (with lateral + posterior seta tufts)		14	1	3			20	20	600	3	D	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20			
	Chilopoda	10	centipedes > 5mm flat. body, forcipulae, 1 pair of legs/seg. (> 15)						0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		20	centipedes < 5mm or Geophilomorpha order						0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Hexapoda	Symphyla	20	slender antennae, 12 pair of legs (in adult), cerci						0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
	Paupoda	20	small, pale, branching antennae, 9-11 pairs of legs						0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
	Collembola*	01	springtails: length > 2mm, complex pigm., developed appendages		1					1	33	0	E	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0				
		02	pigmented, well-developed appendages and eyes		2	1	2			2	167	1	D	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2			
		04	small size, evident pigmentation, medium appendages		7	4	5			4	533	2	D	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4			
		06	uniform pigmentation, small appendages, developed eyes		2					20	6	67	0	E	6	0	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0				
	08	scarce pigmentation, very small appendages, reduced eyes		20	20	14				8	1800	7	C	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8				
	10	very small size, no pigmentation, reduced furca		9	5	3				10	567	2	D	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10				
	20	no pigmentation and no furca or Neelidae, short appendages		20	35	50				20	3500	13	C	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20				
	Diptura	20	no eyes or pigm., long abdomen + pincer-like or moniliform cerci		2	2	5			20	20	300	1	D	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20				
Protura	20	coneheads: conical head, no eyes or antennae, 1 st legs forward			2				20	20	67	0	E	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	0	20	0	20	0	20	0	20	0	20	0					
Hexapoda / Insecta	Coleoptera	01	beetles: dark, sclerotized elytra and protorax big and mobile:		1					1	33	0	E	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0					
		05	epigeic forms							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
		10	+5 EMI points each character: • body length < 2mm;							1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
		15	• depigmentation (tan/brown); • reduction/absence of eyes;								0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
		20	• reduction/absence of wings								0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
	-L_10	larva, 3 pairs of legs, commonly sclerotized head capsule		1					10	10	33	0	E	10	0	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0					
	Diptera	01	flies: 2 wings and 2 halteres			1	3			1	1	133	0	D	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1				
		-L_10	fly larva, mostly no legs, small or absent head		3	1				10	10	133	1	D	10	10	0	0	10	10	0	10	10	0	10	10	0	10	10	0	10	10					
	Hymenoptera	01	4 wings, antennae longer than heads							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
		05	ants: formicidae, geniculate antenn. globose abd. with petiole(s)							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Hemiptera	01	piercing-sucking mouthparts							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Psocoptera	01	booklice and barklice: hypognath mouth apparatus, long antennae							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Thysanoptera	01	thrips: fringed wings, abdomen with 11 segments							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Embioptera	10	webspinners: enlarged tarsi in 1 st pair of legs, elong. abd.(10 seg.)							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Dermaptera	01	earwigs: dark colour, 2 forceps-like cerci							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Extra biological form (with EMI) [§]		Name of less frequent BF		Lepidoptera-L_10		1			10	10	33	0	E	0	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0	10	0						
Extra biological form (with EMI) [§]		Name of 2 nd less frequent BF		not_observed					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Other biological forms (with EMI) [§]		All other BF names in "notes", tot. abundances and sum of EMIs							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
		Dry soil weight (kg) of replicate		1,023		1,216		1,230						QBS indices		value		SA [¶]		Tot. ab.m ²		Tot.ab.class		R1		R2		R3		R1-R2		R1-R3		R2-R3			
		Latitude (decimal degrees)		38,12088		38,12046		38,12099						QBS-ar		167		0,56		26967		A		101		126		141		63		98		46			
		Longitude (decimal degrees)		15,66751		15,66748		15,66701						QBS-ar_BF		208		0,46						141		151		165		64		98		46			

Notes (juvenile forms, family, doubts)↓

Abundance range	A	B	C	D	E	0
Specimen's number (n) per replicate	n≥200	50≤n<200	10≤n<5			